

Supplementary Material

Deep Brain Sound Stimulation for Weight Management: Precision Auditory Stimulation

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1. Detailed Treatment Modalities for Weight Management

1.1 Behavioral and Lifestyle Interventions

- **Cognitive Behavioral Therapy for Weight Management (CBT-WM):** CBT-WM addresses behavioral and psychological factors contributing to weight gain. Core components include:
 - **Self-Monitoring:** Tracking food intake, physical activity, and weight to increase awareness of eating patterns and triggers.
 - **Stimulus Control:** Managing environmental cues that lead to overeating, such as removing unhealthy snacks from the home.
 - **Cognitive Restructuring:** Challenging and replacing negative thought patterns related to food and body image with healthier beliefs.
 - **Behavioral Goal Setting:** Developing specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) goals for weight loss, physical activity, and healthy eating (Spring et al., 2020).
- **Mindfulness-Based Interventions for Weight Management (MBIs):** MBIs, including Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) and Mindfulness-Based Eating Awareness Training (MB-EAT), focus on:
 - **Non-judgmental Awareness:** Enhancing present-moment awareness of hunger and satiety cues.
 - **Binge Eating Reduction:** Implementing strategies to decrease episodes of binge eating and stress-driven eating.
 - **Healthy Relationship with Food:** Cultivating a mindful relationship with food through meditation and focused breathing practices (Mason et al., 2016).

- **Structured Physical Activity Programs:** Regular physical activity is essential for weight loss and obesity prevention. Recommendations include:
 - **Aerobic Exercise:** Engaging in activities like walking, running, or cycling for at least 150–300 minutes per week at moderate intensity.
 - **Resistance Training:** Performing strength training exercises 2–3 times per week to maintain or increase muscle mass.
 - **Lifestyle Activity Integration:** Incorporating strategies such as walking into daily routines or using stairs instead of elevators (Jakicic et al., 2018).
- **Group-Based Weight Loss Programs:** Programs like Weight Watchers offer social support, accountability, and structured education on diet and exercise. Peer support enhances adherence to weight loss goals and improves outcomes (Hartmann-Boyce et al., 2014).

1.2 Nutritional and Dietary Interventions

- **Caloric Deficit Diets:** Reducing daily caloric intake is fundamental for weight loss.
 - **Moderate Caloric Restriction:** A reduction of 500–750 kcal/day for sustainable weight loss of 1–2 pounds per week.
 - **Portion Control and Meal Planning:** Managing portion sizes and encouraging consistent meal patterns (Basolo et al., 2021).
- **Specific Diet Plans:** Various diet plans have shown effectiveness in promoting weight loss and metabolic health:
 - **Mediterranean Diet:** Rich in whole grains, vegetables, fruits, nuts, seeds, olive oil, and lean proteins. Linked to sustained weight loss and reduced risk of chronic diseases (Chee et al., 2024).

- **Low-Carbohydrate Diets:** Emphasize low carbohydrate intake and high fat/protein consumption. Effective for short-term weight loss but may present long-term adherence challenges (Petridou et al., 2019).
- **Intermittent Fasting:** Patterns like time-restricted eating (16:8) or alternate-day fasting reduce caloric intake while improving metabolic markers (Stockman et al., 2018).
- **Plant-Based Diets:** Vegetarian and vegan diets promote satiety and weight loss while improving heart health (Barnard et al., 2015).
- **Meal Replacement Therapy:** Meal replacement products provide structured calorie control, useful for individuals struggling with meal planning or portion control (Astbury et al., 2018).

1.3 Pharmacological Interventions

- **GLP-1 Receptor Agonists:**
 - **Semaglutide (Wegovy) and Liraglutide (Saxenda):** Mimic the hormone glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), reducing appetite, increasing satiety, and slowing gastric emptying. Demonstrate significant weight loss effects when combined with lifestyle modifications (Wilding et al., 2021).
- **Other Appetite Suppressants:**
 - **Phentermine:** A sympathomimetic appetite suppressant approved for short-term use.
 - **Combination Medications:** Drugs like phentermine/topiramate (Qsymia) or naltrexone/bupropion (Contrave) combine appetite suppression with mood

regulation or cravings reduction. Typically prescribed for individuals with a BMI ≥ 30 or ≥ 27 with comorbidities (Apovian et al., 2015).

- **Lipase Inhibitors:**
 - **Orlistat (Alli, Xenical):** Inhibits pancreatic lipase, reducing fat absorption in the gut. Used as an adjunct to diet and exercise but can cause gastrointestinal side effects (Kwon et al., 2022).
- **Emerging Therapies:**
 - **GIP/GLP-1 Dual Agonists:** Drugs like tirzepatide target multiple pathways involved in weight regulation and glucose metabolism, showing promising results in clinical trials (Jastreboff et al., 2022).

1.4 Non-Invasive Neuromodulation Techniques

Emerging non-invasive neuromodulation techniques are being explored for their potential in appetite and metabolic regulation.

- **Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS):** Utilizes magnetic fields to stimulate specific brain regions involved in appetite control and energy balance. Repetitive TMS over the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex can reduce food cravings and caloric intake, suggesting potential for weight management (Kim et al., 2019).
- **Transcranial Direct Current Stimulation (tDCS):** Applies a low electrical current to modulate neuronal activity. Targeting the prefrontal cortex may influence eating behaviors by enhancing self-control and reducing impulsivity, aiding weight loss efforts (Orrù et al., 2022).

1.5 Surgical Interventions

- **Bariatric Surgery:** Recommended for individuals with severe obesity (BMI ≥ 40 , or ≥ 35 with comorbidities) who have not achieved significant weight loss through other methods.

Common procedures include:

- **Roux-en-Y Gastric Bypass:** Reduces stomach size and reroutes the small intestine, limiting food intake and absorption.
 - **Sleeve Gastrectomy:** Removes a large portion of the stomach to reduce food capacity and decrease hunger hormones like ghrelin.
 - **Adjustable Gastric Banding:** Places a band around the upper stomach to create a small pouch, though its use has declined due to lower efficacy compared to other procedures. Bariatric surgery leads to significant and sustained weight loss and improvements in comorbidities but involves surgical risks and requires lifelong dietary adherence (Arterburn et al., 2020).
- **Endoscopic Procedures:** Minimally invasive alternatives to bariatric surgery, such as intragastric balloons or endoscopic sleeve gastroplasty, are emerging as less invasive options for individuals with moderate obesity (Sharaiha et al., 2017).

1.6 Other Emerging Interventions

- **Injectable Medical Devices:** New injectable hydrogel therapies expand in the stomach to promote a feeling of fullness, reducing calorie intake.
- **Gut Microbiome Modulation:** Strategies such as probiotics, prebiotics, and fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) show potential for improving metabolic health (Van Hul & Cani, 2023).

- **Digital Health and Wearables:** Mobile apps, wearable fitness trackers, and telehealth platforms monitor dietary habits, physical activity, and weight, providing personalized feedback and enhancing accountability (Patel et al., 2015).

1.7 Challenges and Limitations

- **Behavioral and Lifestyle Interventions:** Require significant time and commitment, potentially limiting accessibility and adherence (Hartmann-Boyce et al., 2014).
- **Nutritional and Dietary Interventions:** Long-term adherence is challenging due to social, psychological, and metabolic factors (Thomas et al., 2014; Basolo et al., 2021).
- **Pharmacological Interventions:** Associated with side effects and limited long-term usability (Apovian et al., 2015; Wilding et al., 2021).
- **Surgical and Endoscopic Interventions:** Effective but involve surgical risks and require lifelong dietary adjustments (Arterburn et al., 2020; Sharaiha et al., 2017).
- **Non-Invasive Neuromodulation Techniques:** Limited by high costs, accessibility, and insufficient long-term data (Kim et al., 2019; Orrù et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022).
- **Emerging Technologies and Complementary Approaches:** Early-stage research with limited established efficacy (Van Hul & Cani, 2023; Patel et al., 2015).
- **Psychosocial and Environmental Factors:** Significant impact on weight management efforts, often not comprehensively addressed by current treatments (Zhu et al., 2021).

The existing landscape of weight management treatments ranges from behavioral and nutritional approaches to pharmacological, neuromodulatory, and surgical interventions. Each modality presents unique benefits, limitations, and adherence challenges. Understanding these complexities provides a context in which Deep Brain Sound Stimulation (DBSS), as a non-invasive, user-

friendly auditory therapy, may offer a complementary or alternative option by potentially improving accessibility, adherence, and patient satisfaction.

2. Mechanisms of Action and Scientific Evidence for DBSS in Weight Management

This section provides an in-depth examination of the theoretical foundations and empirical support for DBSS, expanding upon the concepts introduced in the main manuscript's Methods and Discussion.

2.1 Mechanisms of Action

- **Targeted Neural Synchronization for Appetite and Metabolism Regulation:** DBSS aims to influence neural synchronization by delivering specific auditory frequencies targeting neural circuits involved in appetite regulation and metabolic control. Frequency selection is based on theoretical models related to neural oscillations associated with appetite regulation (Chee et al., 2024; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017).
- **Neurotransmitter Modulation without Pharmacological Intervention:** DBSS potentially influences neurotransmitter systems involved in weight regulation, including dopamine and serotonin, without the need for pharmacological treatments. This modulation may support stress-related eating reduction and enhance motivation for healthy behaviors (Bhattacharya et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2023).
- **Hormonal and Peptide Modulation for Metabolic Balance:** By targeting hypothalamic nuclei, DBSS may influence the release of metabolic hormones and peptides such as leptin, peptide YY (PYY), and neuropeptide Y (NPY), which play roles in appetite control and energy expenditure (Morton et al., 2014; Steinert et al., 2017).

- **Neuroplasticity for Long-Term Behavioral Changes:** DBSS may enhance neuroplasticity in regions associated with impulse control and reward processing, fostering resilience against habitual overeating and promoting sustainable lifestyle changes (Attokaren et al., 2023; Bhattacharya et al., 2021).

2.2 Scientific Evidence

Research on auditory-based neural modulation supports DBSS's potential in targeting brain regions associated with appetite control and metabolic regulation. Auditory-driven synchronization can enhance connectivity between regions involved in impulse control and stress response, such as the prefrontal cortex and hypothalamic areas, potentially reducing cravings and emotional eating (Chee et al., 2024; Mesgarani & Chang, 2012).

Neuroimaging studies demonstrate that targeted auditory stimulation can activate pathways linked to hunger and satiety regulation, such as the hypothalamus and brainstem areas associated with the vagus nerve. This alignment of brain activity with the body's natural appetite-regulating systems promotes healthier eating behaviors and reduces reliance on pharmacological interventions for weight control (Chee et al., 2024; Seeck et al., 2017).

Studies indicate that sound-based neural entrainment can enhance connectivity between regions like the prefrontal cortex and hypothalamus, crucial for regulating cravings and metabolic balance (Thut et al., 2011; Herrmann et al., 2016). Additionally, auditory stimulation may influence neurotransmitter pathways, including dopamine and serotonin, which are integral to managing stress and motivation (Garcia-Argibay et al., 2019; Bhattacharya et al., 2021).

3. Technical Specifications and Protocol

3.1 Frequency Selection and Modulation

- **Frequency Pairs:** Each DBSS session employs specific primary and secondary frequency pairs based on theoretical models related to neural oscillations involved in appetite regulation (Chee et al., 2024; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017). The primary frequency engages broader cortical areas, while the secondary frequency targets specific subregions defined by Brodmann areas for enhanced precision (Zilles, 2018; Ala et al., 2018).
- **Modulation Rates:** Secondary frequencies are modulated at stable rates to ensure reliable neural entrainment and reproducibility (Voskuhl et al., 2018).

3.2 Duration and Scheduling

- **Duration:**
 - **Weight Loss Therapy:** Single 35-minute session targeting key appetite and metabolic regulation pathways.
 - **Obesity Therapy:** Two sessions:
 - **Session 1:** 35-minute session similar to Weight Loss Protocol.
 - **Session 2:** 29-minute session focusing on additional brain regions related to gut-brain signaling and emotional regulation.
- **Scheduling Guidelines:**
 - **Weight Loss Therapy:** Users can repeat the single session multiple times a day if needed.
 - **Obesity Therapy:** Alternate between Session 1 and Session 2 daily.
- **Consistency Encouragement:** Structured schedules and reminders promote consistent use to maximize potential therapeutic benefits.

3.3 Equipment

- **Tone Generators:** High-precision tone generator software ensures accurate frequency control, critical for targeting weight-regulatory neural circuits (Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017).
- **Headphones:** Over-ear circumaural headphones are recommended for consistent, high-quality auditory signal delivery. Users are advised to verify headphone compatibility using the app's integrated sound test before initiating therapy (Chen, 2022).

3.4 Mapping and Targeting Brain Regions

- **Identifying Brain Regions:** DBSS references detailed cortical and subcortical maps to guide stimulation. By integrating frequency-following responses (FFRs) (Cabral-Calderin & Henry, 2022; Kraus & White-Schwoch, 2015) and theoretical frameworks for neural targeting, DBSS aims to engage hypothalamic and prefrontal circuits implicated in appetite regulation. This precision enables entrainment without excessive activation of hyperactive regions.
- **Validation Through Sensory Feedback:** User feedback during sessions and ongoing research support frequency settings and targeting accuracy (Chee et al., 2024).

3.5 Reproducibility Protocol

To ensure reproducibility, researchers should follow these steps:

1. **Frequency Selection:** Choose primary and secondary frequency pairs based on established neural oscillation patterns linked to appetite and metabolic regulation (Zilles, 2018; Ala et al., 2018).
2. **Setting Modulation Rates:** Apply precise modulation techniques for secondary frequencies, maintaining stable rates throughout the session to ensure consistent neural engagement.

3. **Session Planning:** Allocate at least 3 minutes of stimulation per targeted region to ensure adequate neural alignment. Although no inferential statistics were conducted in the current observational study, future research should incorporate more rigorous methods (Stein et al., 2020).
4. **Equipment Setup:** Utilize calibrated tone generators and high-quality headphones. Confirm headphone compatibility and stable frequency delivery to induce rapid neural entrainment (Kobayashi et al., 2024; Aderinto et al., 2024).
5. **Mapping and Validation:** Confirm engagement through user feedback and ongoing research, ensuring that targeted weight-regulatory regions are accurately engaged and that stimulation protocols are effective (Chee et al., 2024; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017).

3.6 Intellectual Property Considerations

Certain aspects, such as detailed frequency mappings and modulation techniques, remain proprietary to protect intellectual property during ongoing development and patenting. While some technical details are confidential, the provided protocol offers sufficient guidance for reproducibility and independent validation (Chen, 2022).

4. Detailed Scientific Evidence, Case Reports, and Therapy Sessions

4.1 Scientific Evidence

DBSS builds on research in auditory brainwave entrainment and neural synchronization, aiming to regulate appetite, enhance metabolic control, and improve emotional resilience through targeted neural modulation. Specific frequency bands influence mood and cognitive processing:

- **Alpha Waves (8–12 Hz):** Associated with relaxation and anxiety reduction.
- **Beta Waves (13–30 Hz):** Linked to focus and cognitive control.

- **Gamma Waves (>30 Hz):** Support higher-order cognitive functions and neuroplasticity (Herrmann et al., 2016; Thut et al., 2011).

4.2 Case Studies

- **Case Study by Dogan et al. (2023):** A 24-year-old male with a porencephalic cyst and right-sided hemiparesis underwent DBSS therapy. Over one year, significant improvements in motor control and a reduction in cyst size were observed. This case provides insights into DBSS's capacity to modulate neural circuits involved in emotional regulation and stress responses, relevant to weight management.

4.3 Applications in Weight Management

DBSS targets specific brain regions implicated in weight management, focusing on appetite regulation, metabolic balance, and emotional resilience (STable 1).

Type	Brain Region	Connections/Function	Treatment
GM	Peptides (PYY, VIP, PP, NPY)	Regulate appetite and satiety: - PYY (Peptide YY): Reduces food intake by suppressing appetite (Steinert et al., 2017). - VIP (Vasoactive Intestinal Peptide): Affects gastrointestinal motility and energy expenditure (Vu et al., 2023). - PP (Pancreatic Polypeptide): Acts on hunger centers in the hypothalamus, reducing appetite (Alhabeeb et al., 2021). - NPY (Neuropeptide Y): Typically promotes	Both Weight Loss and Obesity programs

		hunger; modulated stimulation can help balance appetite (Steinert et al., 2017).	
GM	Dorsomedial Hypothalamic Nucleus (DMN)	Releases GnRH, CRH, TRH, and somatostatin, which influence appetite, metabolism, and stress response (Timper & Brüning, 2017).	Both Weight Loss and Obesity programs
GM	Ventromedial Hypothalamic Nucleus (VMN)	Leptin-sensitive, suppresses hunger and promotes satiety, playing a crucial role in energy homeostasis (Timper & Brüning, 2017).	Both Weight Loss and Obesity programs
GM	Vagus Nerve (Liver, GI System)	Regulates digestion, nutrient absorption, and caloric intake through gut-brain communication (Van Hul & Cani, 2023).	Obesity program
GM	Vagus Nerve (Gallbladder, Large Intestine)	Obesity program	Obesity program
WM	Raphe Nucleus to Amygdala	Serotonergic pathways modulate anxiety and stress, supporting emotional resilience and reducing emotional eating (Ouakinin et al., 2018).	Obesity program
WM	Dopamine Pathways (VTA to Caudate)	Regulates reward sensitivity, cravings, and motivation, helping to control emotional eating (Wallace et al., 2021).	Obesity program

	Nucleus, Globus Pallidus, DLPFC)		
WM	Dopamine Pathways (VTA to Putamen, Thalamus, dmPFC)	Enhances emotional regulation and reduces stress-related eating (Wallace et al., 2021).	Obesity program
WM	Raphe Nucleus to Subgenual Gyrus, BNST	Serotonergic pathways help regulate stress and emotional responses, supporting appetite control (Aklan et al., 2023).	Obesity program
WM	DLPFC to BNST	Assists with impulse control and stress regulation, reducing binge eating behaviors (Heinitz et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019).	Obesity program
WM	dmPFC, vmPFC to BNST	Regulates stress and emotional processing, enhancing self-control over food intake (Heinitz et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019).	Obesity program
GM	Temporal Pole	Involved in emotional processing, supporting self-regulation and reducing emotional eating tendencies (Coppin, 2016).	Obesity program

STable 1: Details of DBSS Sessions for Weight Loss and Obesity Treatment

This table outlines targeted brain regions and their connections relevant to appetite regulation, emotional resilience, and metabolic control.

4.4 Avoidance of Hyperactive Regions

DBSS avoids direct stimulation of certain brain regions that could exacerbate dysregulation, such as the amygdala and anterior insula. By focusing on regions that promote satiety and emotional regulation, DBSS minimizes the risk of enhancing maladaptive patterns (Bhattacharya et al., 2021; Hemmerling & Hofer, 2022; Stuber & Wise, 2016).

4.5 Integration with DBSS Development for Weight Management

- **DBSS Protocol for Weight Management:** Targets brain regions involved in appetite, metabolic balance, and emotional eating, including DMN and VMN, influencing neurotransmitter pathways like dopamine and serotonin.
- **Frequency Selection:** Based on theoretical models related to neural oscillations in appetite regulation (Chee et al., 2024; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017).
- **Session Structure:** Sequential engagement of regions regulating appetite and emotional control through specific session durations.
- **Scientific Validation:** Ongoing research supports the alignment of DBSS protocols with findings in weight regulation neurobiology (Chee et al., 2024; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017).

4.6 Additional Scientific Evidence

- **Neuroplasticity Enhancement:** Non-invasive brain stimulation techniques like DBSS may promote neuroplasticity in regions crucial for appetite regulation and stress resilience, aiding long-term weight management (Heinitz et al., 2017; Chatterjee et al., 2021).

- **Functional Connectivity Improvement:** Enhanced connectivity between the prefrontal cortex and hypothalamic regions supports better self-control over food intake and stabilizes metabolic function (Kim et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2019).
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5. Development and Research Environment Details

5.1 App Development and Deployment

- **Platform Availability:** DBSS protocol is accessible globally via Google Play, Gumroad, and the Apple App Store, supporting 11 languages to enhance accessibility across diverse user groups.
- **User Interface and Experience:** Features an intuitive interface with clear instructions on headphone placement, session preparation, and post-session relaxation. Includes therapy reminders and progress tracking to encourage adherence.

5.2 Financial Sustainability and Resource Allocation

- **Revenue Model:** Utilizes a freemium approach, offering free access to an initial session and complete treatment for a one-time fee of \$30–\$50.
- **Resource Allocation:** Revenue supports ongoing research and development, refinement of protocols, and expansion of therapeutic offerings.

5.3 Participant Recruitment and Feedback

- **Broad Participant Recruitment:** Facilitates wide recruitment through the app-based format, allowing global access.
- **Feedback Collection:** Encourages feedback via in-app surveys to assess therapy effectiveness, user satisfaction, and adherence patterns.
- **Feedback Metrics:**

- **Session Helpfulness:** Users rate the effectiveness of sessions.
- **Perceived Improvement:** Participants report symptom relief percentages.
- **Adherence Tracking:** Monitors engagement with therapy sessions.
- **Iterative Feedback Loop:** Continuous feedback informs protocol refinement and optimization.

5.4 Ethical Standards and Data Handling

- **User Consent and Data Privacy:** Complies with GDPR and app platform policies. Users provide implied consent through app usage and Privacy Policy acceptance.
- **Data Protection Measures:**
 - **User Data Anonymization:** All data is anonymized and aggregated to prevent identification.
 - **Data Security:** Implemented encryption and restricted access, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.
 - **Transaction Data:** Managed securely by platforms like Apple, with only anonymized demographic data accessed for research purposes.
- **Risk Minimization:**
 - **Health Guidelines:** Users with specific health conditions are advised to consult healthcare professionals before using DBSS.
 - **Conflict of Interest Management:** Development and research are self-funded to minimize bias.
- **User Support and Safety:** Includes FAQs, tutorials, and customer support to assist users. Safety prompts and guidelines are integrated to minimize risks.

- **Compliance with Ethical Standards:** Adheres to the Declaration of Helsinki and relevant local regulations, ensuring ethical research practices.
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6. Safety, Effectiveness, and User Satisfaction Data

6.1 User Statistics and Satisfaction Rate

- **Total Users and Satisfaction Rate:**
 - **Weight Loss Program:** 47 users
 - **Obesity Program:** 131 users
 - **Overall:** 178 users with a 0% refund rate, indicating a 100% inferred satisfaction rate based on purchase behavior and engagement metrics.
- **Broader User Base:** This analysis focuses on Apple App Store data due to its comprehensive engagement metrics. Other platforms like Google Play and Gumroad have limited data.
- **Effectiveness Metrics:** Limited survey responses render effectiveness metrics preliminary and exploratory. No definitive effectiveness percentages are reported. Future research with larger sample sizes is necessary.

6.2 Safety Profile

- **Safety Record:** No reported adverse effects among users of the Weight Loss and Obesity programs, suggesting a favorable safety profile for DBSS.
- **Side Effects:** The absence of reported side effects supports DBSS as a safe intervention for home-based use. While minor, transient effects like dizziness are theoretically possible, none were observed in this study.

6.3 Effectiveness Metrics

- **Overall Effectiveness:** Due to limited survey responses, effectiveness metrics are considered preliminary and exploratory.
- **Confidence Interval:** Not applicable due to the small sample size and limited survey participation.

6.4 Adherence Strategies for Weight Management Treatments

- **Clear Instructions:** Comprehensive app instructions on headphone placement, session preparation, and usage schedules facilitate user engagement.
 - **Usage Scheduling:** Structured session schedules promote consistent use, essential for potential therapeutic benefits.
 - **Encouragement of Consistent Use:** Features like session reminders and progress tracking support adherence, enhancing DBSS's potential effectiveness (Kelders et al., 2012; Fry & Neff, 2009).
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7. Long-term Efficacy and Safety Data

7.1 Usage and Safety Data

Across all platforms, DBSS has facilitated approximately 12,000 complete treatments and over 3 million sessions for various conditions, including weight loss and obesity, without major safety concerns. Users consistently report positive experiences, and no significant side effects were observed.

7.2 Long-term Efficacy

- **Weight Loss Outcomes:** Preliminary data suggest that DBSS may support sustainable weight loss by targeting neural circuits involved in appetite control and metabolic regulation (Steinert et al., 2017; Timper & Brüning, 2017).

- **Consistency of Therapeutic Effects:** Regular engagement with DBSS may stabilize appetite suppression and improve metabolic efficiency, though formal longitudinal studies are needed for confirmation.
- **User Retention and Symptom Recurrence:** High user retention rates and minimal reports of symptom recurrence indicate sustained therapeutic benefits, though more extensive studies are required.

7.3 Influence of Adherence

- **Importance of Protocol Consistency:** Adherence to the DBSS protocol is critical for therapeutic success, enhancing neural engagement and promoting sustained appetite suppression (Bhattacharya et al., 2021).
- **Supportive App Features:** Personalized reminders and progress tracking support consistent use, essential for maximizing therapeutic benefits.
- **Encouragement of Consistent Use:** Structured schedules and clear guidance encourage adherence, enhancing DBSS's overall effectiveness.

7.4 Impact of App Store Policies on User Engagement

- **Effect of Policy Changes:** In 2017, Apple App Store policy changes required individual therapy apps to be consolidated into a single container app, reducing visibility of standalone therapies.
- **Sales Data Trends:** Despite reduced visibility, the Weight Loss and Obesity programs maintained a 0% refund rate among 178 users, indicating sustained satisfaction and engagement.

- **User Acquisition Challenges:** Policy changes impacted new user acquisitions, but existing users continued to report strong outcomes. Future strategies may include enhanced in-app marketing to mitigate reduced discoverability (SFig. 1, 2).

SFigure 1: Impact of App Store Policy Changes on Download Rates

This figure illustrates Vital Tones Weight Loss app sales on the Apple App Store over time, showing a decline in downloads after the 2017 policy change to a container app format. Existing users maintain high satisfaction and engagement despite reduced new user acquisitions.

SFigure 2: Impact of App Store Policy Changes on Download Rates

This figure illustrates Vital Tones Obesity app sales on the Apple App Store over time, showing a decline in downloads after the 2017 policy change to a container app format. Existing users maintain high satisfaction and engagement despite reduced new user acquisitions.

8. User Demographics and Adherence

8.1 User Demographics

- **Age Distribution:** Majority of users are aged 25–54 years, aligning with demographics seeking weight management solutions (Nguyen et al., 2021).
- **Gender Distribution:** Predominantly female, consistent with higher engagement in weight loss programs due to societal pressures and proactive health-seeking behaviors (Roberts et al., 2019). Male engagement is increasing, particularly for obesity-focused therapies.

- **Global Reach:** Significant usage in North America, Europe, and Asia, reflecting global obesity trends and demand for non-invasive interventions (STable 2).

8.2 Engagement and Adherence Patterns

- **Initial and Sustained Engagement:** High engagement in the first month, driven by initial motivation. Sustained engagement depends on user experience and perceived effectiveness (Spring et al., 2020).
- **Adherence Challenges:** Factors such as time constraints and lack of immediate results can affect adherence. Clear instructions and realistic expectations help mitigate drop-off rates (Patel et al., 2015).
- **Completion and Retention:** Structured session schedules and progress tracking correlate with higher adherence and completion rates, similar to other digital weight management tools (Astbury et al., 2018).

8.3 Demographic Influence on Effectiveness

- **Age and Effectiveness:** Younger adults may experience higher engagement and effectiveness due to greater familiarity with digital tools. Older adults may require additional guidance.
- **Gender Trends:** Women report greater satisfaction and adherence, while men seek obesity-focused solutions for health-related reasons (Jastreboff et al., 2022).
- **Cultural and Regional Variations:** Cultural attitudes toward weight management influence app engagement. Linguistic adaptability enhances effectiveness across diverse populations (Van Hul & Cani, 2023).

8.4 Enhancing Adherence and User Experience

- **Support Resources:** Includes FAQs, reminders, and tutorials to guide users, encouraging adherence and making the experience seamless (Spring et al., 2020).
- **Community and Feedback Opportunities:** In-app surveys and optional forums foster engagement and allow continuous improvement of protocols. Peer communities can increase motivation and adherence (Patel et al., 2015).

8.5 Generalizability

- **Diverse User Base:** Broad geographical reach and multilingual support enhance the generalizability of findings, ensuring applicability across different demographics and cultural contexts (Nguyen et al., 2021).

Territory	Weight Loss Units Downloaded	Obesity Units Downloaded
USA and Canada	16	34
Europe	12	46
Asia Pacific	13	30
Latin America and The Caribbean	5	19
Africa, The Middle East, and India	2	2

STable 2: Geographic Distribution of Vital Tones App Downloads

This table presents the distribution of app downloads by territory for both Weight Loss and Obesity programs.

9. Detailed Methodology

9.1 Data Collection

This observational study utilizes anonymized and aggregated user data from the Apple App Store to evaluate DBSS therapy for weight management. The observational design was chosen to collect exploratory data from a diverse user base without the constraints of controlled trials. Effectiveness metrics are preliminary and exploratory due to limited survey responses. Primary data sources include app engagement metrics and refund requests, with a 0% refund rate serving as an indirect indicator of user satisfaction.

9.2 Calculation of User Satisfaction and Effectiveness

- **User Satisfaction:** Calculated based on the absence of refund requests.

$$\% \text{ of Users satisfied with treatment} = \frac{\text{Number of Users with No Refund Requests}}{\text{Total Number of Users}} \times 100$$

- **Effectiveness:** Due to limited survey responses, effectiveness metrics are considered preliminary and exploratory.
- **Confidence Interval:** Not applicable due to the lack of substantial survey-based effectiveness data.

9.3 Addressing Selection Bias

The study acknowledges potential selection bias from self-selected users who chose to purchase the DBSS app. The absence of a control group limits causal inferences. Future research should incorporate randomized sampling and control groups to enhance validity and reliability.

9.4 Reproducibility Protocol

To ensure reproducibility, researchers should follow these steps:

1. **Frequency Selection:** Choose primary and secondary frequency pairs based on neural oscillation patterns relevant to appetite control and metabolic regulation.

2. **Setting Modulation Rates:** Apply precise modulation techniques for secondary frequencies, maintaining stable rates throughout the session to ensure consistent neural engagement.
 3. **Session Planning:** Structure sessions to balance stimulation across targeted regions, allocating sufficient time (minimum of three minutes) for each location to ensure optimal neural engagement.
 4. **Equipment Setup:** Utilize calibrated tone generators and circumaural headphones to deliver accurate, consistent auditory stimuli. Verify headphone compatibility using the app's integrated sound test before initiating therapy.
 5. **Mapping and Validation:** Confirm engagement through user feedback and ongoing research, ensuring that targeted weight-regulatory regions are accurately engaged and that stimulation protocols are effective (Chee et al., 2024; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017).
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10: Detailed Comparison with Existing Treatments

10.1 Efficacy

- **Behavioral Interventions:**
 - **CBT-WM:** Effective for 5–10% body weight reduction over 6 months to 1 year (Spring et al., 2020), contingent on sustained engagement and accessibility.
 - **MBIs:** Significant reductions in binge eating and emotional eating patterns, with modest weight loss (Mason et al., 2016).
- **Pharmacotherapy:**

- **GLP-1 Receptor Agonists:** Substantial efficacy in promoting weight loss, up to 15% body weight reduction when combined with lifestyle modifications (Wilding et al., 2021).
- **Other Appetite Suppressants:** Effective in the short term but associated with dependency and cardiovascular side effects (Apovian et al., 2015).
- **Surgical Interventions:**
 - **Bariatric Surgery:** Highly effective, resulting in 20–30% body weight reduction and improvements in comorbidities, but involves surgical risks and requires lifelong adherence (Arterburn et al., 2020).
- **Non-Invasive Neuromodulation Techniques:**
 - **TMS and tDCS:** Moderate efficacy in reducing food cravings and caloric intake, limited by high costs and insufficient long-term data (Kim et al., 2019; Orrù et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2022).
- **DBSS:**
 - **Therapeutic Effects:** Utilizes calibrated auditory frequencies to modulate neural circuits involved in appetite control and metabolic regulation.
 - **Efficacy Rate:** Preliminary user data indicate an inferred satisfaction rate of 100% based on a 0% refund rate among 178 users. Effectiveness rates are exploratory and require validation through larger, controlled studies.
 - **Mechanistic Advantages:** Offers a non-invasive approach that directly targets neural circuits without systemic side effects, positioning DBSS as a potentially safer and more user-friendly alternative (Chee et al., 2024; Zoefel & VanRullen, 2017).

10.2 Safety

- **Behavioral Interventions:** Generally safe but require significant time and effort.
- **Pharmacotherapy:** Associated with side effects and limited long-term usability (Apovian et al., 2015).
- **Surgical Interventions:** Involves surgical risks and requires lifelong dietary adherence (Arterburn et al., 2020).
- **DBSS:** Demonstrates an excellent safety record with no reported adverse effects in this study. Rare, mild side effects like dizziness were not observed, supporting DBSS as a safe intervention.

10.3 Cost

- **Behavioral Interventions:** In-person sessions can be costly over time; digital alternatives are more affordable but may lack personalized guidance.
- **Pharmacotherapy:** Ongoing costs include prescription fees and doctor visits.
- **Surgical Interventions:** High upfront costs, often exceeding \$20,000, with additional expenses for follow-up care.
- **DBSS:** One-time cost of \$30–\$50 per program, offering a highly cost-effective solution without recurring expenses.

10.4 Patient Adherence

- **Behavioral Interventions:** Challenging due to the need for significant lifestyle changes; digital versions improve convenience but may lack accountability.
- **Pharmacotherapy:** Side effects and dependency concerns reduce long-term adherence (Wilding et al., 2021).

- **Surgical Interventions:** High adherence post-surgery due to significant weight loss, but requires strict dietary compliance.
- **DBSS:** Offers flexibility and convenience, with high inferred satisfaction rates indicating strong adherence, supported by app features like reminders and clear instructions.

10.5 Additional Advantages

- **Accessibility:** Digital format ensures global availability, bypassing geographic and socioeconomic barriers.
- **Privacy:** Allows users to manage weight privately without clinic visits or group therapy.
- **Ease of Use:** Intuitive app design minimizes the learning curve, making it accessible to users with limited technical skills.
- **Immediate Availability:** Ready for use immediately after download, unlike medications or surgeries requiring prescriptions or appointments.
- **Scalability:** Digital intervention can accommodate an unlimited number of users, addressing global obesity challenges without straining healthcare resources.

10.6 Conclusion

DBSS presents a promising, non-invasive supplement to existing weight management treatments. Its affordability, safety profile, and high inferred user satisfaction suggest potential as a complementary or standalone option for weight loss and obesity management. While preliminary data indicate promising outcomes, further clinical studies, including randomized controlled trials, are necessary to validate its efficacy and explore its integration into comprehensive weight management programs.

11. Ethical Considerations

11.1 Informed Consent and User Privacy

This study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association et al., 2013) and under applicable United States federal regulations governing human subjects research. The analysis involved anonymized, aggregated user data collected through the voluntary use of the Vital Tones mobile application. No personally identifiable information (PII) was collected or stored at any point.

- **Implied Consent through App Use:** By downloading and using the Vital Tones Weight Loss and Obesity app, users agreed to the app's Privacy Policy and the terms of service of the platforms (e.g., Apple App Store) where it is available. These policies clearly state that anonymized data may be used for quality improvement and research purposes.
- **Accessibility of Privacy Policy:** The Privacy Policy is accessible on the Vital Tones website and via the App Store, informing users about data collection and usage practices from the outset.
- **Voluntary Participation:** Users retained full autonomy. They could decline to participate in optional surveys, refrain from using the app, or discontinue use at any time, thereby opting out of data collection and analysis.

11.2 Data Protection and Anonymity

- **Anonymized Data:** No personally identifiable information (PII) was collected. All data were anonymized and aggregated, ensuring that individual users could not be identified.
- **Data Security Measures:** The study adhered to strict data protection protocols, including encryption and restricted access, aligning with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Voigt & Von dem Bussche, 2017).

- **Transaction Data:** Financial transactions were managed by third-party platforms and never linked to personal identities. Only anonymized, aggregate data were used for analysis.
- **Survey Data:** User feedback from optional surveys was de-identified. Providing additional contact information (e.g., email) was optional, and if given, it was kept confidential and solely used for stated purposes.

11.3 Risk Assessment and Minimization

- **Minimal Risk to Participants:** The study involved retrospective analysis of anonymized, routine operational data. No additional interventions were introduced for research, resulting in minimal risk. No physical, psychological, or legal harms were reported.
- **Health and Safety Guidelines:** The app and website provide clear instructions and precautions. Users with conditions such as epilepsy or pregnancy are advised to consult healthcare professionals before using the therapy. Automated safety prompts ensure users are informed of potential considerations before sessions commence.

11.4 Compliance with Ethical Standards

- **Adherence to Guidelines:** This research complies with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association et al., 2013) and U.S. federal regulations for human subjects research (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services et al., 2017).
- **IRB Exemption Justification:** Under U.S. federal regulations (45 CFR 46.104(d)) (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services et al., 2017; Office for Human Research Protections et al., 2017), research involving survey procedures and fully anonymized data that pose minimal risk may be exempt from Institutional Review Board (IRB) review. This

study qualifies for Exemption Category 2, as no identifiable information was collected and no risk would result from data disclosure.

- **Informed Consent:** Informed consent was implied through voluntary engagement and acceptance of the publicly available Privacy Policy. Given the absence of PII and the non-intrusive nature of data collection, no formal written consent was required.
- **Future Ethical Oversight:** While this observational study was exempt, any future controlled or interventional research on DBSS will undergo appropriate formal ethics review to ensure full compliance with evolving regulatory and ethical standards.

11.5 Conflict of Interest and Transparency

- **Conflict of Interest:** The author acknowledges a potential conflict of interest as the developer and seller of the DBSS application. To mitigate bias, the study relies solely on anonymized data and presents findings as preliminary. Independent, external validation through controlled trials and non-affiliated researchers is encouraged to objectively assess DBSS's efficacy and safety.
- **Transparency:** The app's Privacy Policy and terms inform users of data handling practices, ensuring they understand how their anonymized data may be used for service improvement and research.
- **User-Centric Policies:** The design and operational guidelines of the app prioritize user welfare, data confidentiality, and respect for personal autonomy.

11.6 User Safety and Well-being

- **Avoidance of Potential Harm:** Instructions, safety guidelines, and disclaimers are integrated to minimize any potential harm. Users are encouraged to seek professional advice if they have health conditions that might warrant caution.

- **User Support:** Customer support channels are available to address user inquiries, enabling informed decision-making and assistance as needed.

11.7 Conclusion

This study respects established ethical norms, ensuring user privacy, data protection, and participant autonomy. By operating under a minimal-risk, exempt classification under U.S. law—supported by extensive, real-world operational use and transparent data policies—this research aligns with appropriate ethical standards. The findings aim to responsibly contribute to the exploration of DBSS as a potential therapy for Weight Loss and Obesity, while encouraging ongoing scrutiny, external validation, and adherence to best ethical practices.
